

GLOBAL EXPERTISE IN EVENT TOURISM

Mirzayeva A.

PhD-Student,

*Institute of Control Systems,
Baku State University, Azerbaijan*

Abstract

In the system of world tourism development, event tourism has a special and significant place today. In the entire system of world tourism, its share annually increases by 1.5%. The structure of the age composition of tourist flows has also changed significantly. Now the share of travelers under 30 is more than 40% of tourist flows. Event tourism is developing as a more dynamic and active part of the productive forces of the region and therefore contributes to an increase in the resource potential in general. For example, holding major events plays an important role in the revival of cities and makes a significant contribution to increasing the attractiveness of the tourist area, but often becomes the beginning of a branding campaign. If the city already has a strong brand (cultural, tourism), it can contribute to the development of event tourism, which in turn will strengthen it.

Keywords: Event tourism, festival, tourism, culture, international.

Classifications are an important part of the theoretical foundations of both the entire tourism sector and its individual areas. In the modern world, there are more and more events and events that have a certain set of fundamental features, according to which it is possible and necessary to systematize them. Currently, there are many different classifications and criteria by which modern authors structure the events taking place in the world.

According to the main classification we are considering, events are distributed on the basis of the following features:

- the target audience is people who think about the various proposals of tourist enterprises for the implementation of tours. In our case, about visiting festivals, carnivals, etc.

- the concept of events is the most important component, consisting of several points that help to make

the event more popular. So, the concept includes: choosing a goal - what needs to be achieved as a result of the event; market conditions; competitive environment; scale definition; event title; theme of the event; definition of target groups; place and time of the event;

- organization of an event - whether it is a festival, a carnival, some kind of sporting event, each of these events requires a certain approach to implementation.

Thus, we see that event tourism is not a simple "phenomenon" in the life of the country, it requires great attention to itself, both to the organization itself and to the little things that seem insignificant.

Now let us dwell in more detail on the classifications that are currently offered to us by modern authors.

So, O.V. Alekseeva divides event tourism according to the criterion of their form, which shows us the obvious difference in their goals and programs:

Cultural celebrations:	festivals; - carnivals; - commemorative ceremonies; - religious holidays
Political and state:	summits; - political events; - VIP visits
Business and Trade:	meetings, meetings; - fairs, exhibitions
Educational and scientific	conferences; - seminars; - practical exercises
Sport competitions:	among professionals and amateurs; - for spectators and participants
Entertainment:	sports and games for fun
Private events:	weddings; - parties; - meetings
Arts and Entertainment:	concerts; - ceremonies

Some of the events are public, the essence of such events is to create an atmosphere that will be educational, encourage civic pride and bring people together. At the same time, other groups may be created for fun, entertainment, business and competition. In order for these events to be successful, certain opportunities and conditions are required.

The following classification is based on the scale of activities:

- regional - these are events that are important for a particular micro-region (administrative region, city). Such events include, for example, the celebration of the day of the city by the population, the Love Parade in Berlin (Germany);

- national - events that are important for the entire state. So, for example, the celebration of the birthday of

Napoleon Bonaparte, Ajaccio (Corsica); parade of military tattoos in Edinburgh (Scotland);

- international (global) events are usually well-known and popular all over the world, attracting the largest number of tourists. These are such sports events as the Olympics - winter and summer Olympic Games, Formula 1 auto racing; carnival events - Brazilian, Venetian; beauty contests - "Miss World"; festivals - Holland Flower Festival, Cannes Film Festival and others.

Another classification divides activities according to their functional focus into the following groups:

- Congress. The geography of congress events covers almost the whole world. However, the main destinations are Germany, USA and Spain. They account for about 90% of the conference market. The centers of congress tourism are cities that meet the following requirements: availability of the necessary meeting

rooms, convenient transport links, favorable geographical location, high quality of the hospitality industry, leadership or significance in a certain type of human activity (science, culture, business, etc.), architectural attractiveness, the presence of sightseeing objects in the city itself or near it.

- Festival. This type of tourism includes carnivals, song contests, national holidays and beauty festivals. Also among the festival events that attract thousands of tourists include: parades and flower festivals (Holland, Thailand), beauty contests, bullfighting (Spain, Portugal, France), wine festivals (France, Switzerland) and beer (Germany), parade of the Royal Horse Guards in London (UK).

- Sports. International sports events (Olympic Games, Universiades, World and Continental Championships) attract a huge number of people. Among all sporting events, in terms of tourist flows and income, the winter and summer Olympic Games stand out. The Grand Slam tournaments (the most prestigious tennis games held in Melbourne, Wimbledon, Munich and Paris), the Royal Regatta in London, held annually on the River Thames since 1839, the largest yacht race in Europe along the Geneva lake (Switzerland).

- International exhibition and fair. About 80% of the conducted exhibition events are held in the countries of North America and Western Europe. Especially a lot in France, USA, UK and Germany. Examples of traditionally held exhibitions are: the largest car show in Geneva (Switzerland), annual exhibitions of books and printing equipment in Frankfurt am Main (Germany). Air show (international exhibition of aeronautics and rocket science) in Bourges (France).

- Informative. One of the popular areas of this type of tourism is ethnographic tourism - visiting the places of traditional residence of the natives. The most adapted conditions for ethnographic tourism are in the countries of America, Africa, Oceania, Southeast Asia, and in the northern and eastern regions of Russia. Successfully ethnographic travel is developing in the United States, where the culture of the American Indians has become an integral part of the tourism industry. Interest is also growing in the study of natural objects. This includes interesting and rare phenomena (objects) of nature: bird colonies, waterfalls, geysers, caves, seal rookeries.

Festivals are among the most popular events in the event tourism market. "Festivaml (French Festival - festive) is a mass celebration, a show or review of the achievements of musical, theatrical, variety, circus or cinema art." In America, street fairs are also called folk festivals.

So the festivals are divided into:

1) National festivals. At their core, they are associated with certain events in the historical past of countries. For example, the wedding of Crown Prince Ludwig and Princess Teresa of Saxony-Hildburghaus, the Venice Carnival - honoring young men who recaptured stolen girlfriends from Croatian pirates - marked the beginning of Oktoberfest. (Other examples of national festivals are: St. Patrick's Festival in Dublin (Ireland); Festival of Cultures in Berlin (Germany); St. Patrick's Festival in London (UK).)

2) Film and theater festivals. Film festivals are of great interest and popularity among tourists, films and performances shown at festivals receive worldwide recognition. (For example: Cannes Film Festival, Cannes (France); Oberhausen Short Film Festival (Germany); Opera Arts Festival, Verona (Italy).)

3) Music festivals and music competitions. Festivals evoke a lot of emotions and provide an opportunity to get acquainted with many musical groups of the world. (For example: Snow and Symphony Festival, St. Moritz (Switzerland); Jazz Festival in Stockholm (Sweden); Eurovision Music Contest.)

4) Theatrical festivals are a multifaceted social phenomenon, the main advantage of a theatrical performance is the active and obligatory involvement of participants directly in ongoing events. Theatricalization is a special type of socio-cultural activity with an ever-increasing demand for it in the tourism business. (For example: Future Circus Festival, Paris (France); Fringe Festival of Experimental Theaters (Edinburgh, Scotland); Avignon Festival (Avignon, France); Burning Man Contemporary Art Festival.)

5) Gastronomic festivals. The purpose of gastronomic festivals is to enjoy the cuisine of a particular state. However, this goal is not limited to the usual acquaintance with an exotic dish or to eating a huge amount of food. The main thing in such festivals is to understand and enjoy local recipes, which have absorbed the centuries-old customs and traditions of local residents, to understand the culture of cooking national food. With the help of food, the spirit of the people opens up, tourists get the opportunity to understand their mentality. (For example: International Beer Festival, Berlin (Germany); Oktoberfest, Munich (Germany).)

6) Festivals and flower shows are an unforgettable journey. At this time, the whole country in which the festival takes place is buried in flowers, aromas, all residents and tourists from all over the world celebrate the arrival of spring. (For example: Tulip Show (Netherlands); Chelsea Flower Show, London (UK); O-hanami Cherry Viewing (Japan); Bonsai Festival, Nara (Japan).)

It should be said that such events are aimed at public event tours, and people of different incomes become tourists of such events.

Everyone knows the events that made a name for this or that city, region, country. Among the striking examples is the carnival in Rio de Janeiro, which is known on all continents. The Brazilian carnival is confidently kept in the top of tourism among the most visited world events. Another example is the Cannes Film Festival. Also, one of the most massive festivities in the world is the Oktoberfest beer festival.

Budapest has long positioned itself as a "city of festivals", including the Spring and Autumn Festivals, the Budapest Fair and the Sziget Festival. During the week when it passes, young people from all over the world come to the city. Budapest aspires to become one of Europe's leading cultural capitals, attracting large numbers of domestic and international tourists.

Venice enjoys a reputation as one of the "holiday" cities, where the Venice Carnival takes place every

year. Here, for 10 days, the festive atmosphere of the 18th century is reproduced. - traditional ceremonies, cavalcades, all kinds of masquerades and parades replace each other in the colorful and noisy streets. More than 500 thousand tourists from all over the world come to the carnival every year. Among the positive factors of the above brand events are:

- creation of a comfortable living environment;
- stimulation of the tourist flow;
- repositioning of the territory and the formation of a positive image;
- the accumulation of a new cultural heritage and the actualization of the old;
- business development, including in the field of organizing events;
- attracting foreign investment, which will be facilitated by the attractiveness of the region;
- attracting investments from the federal budget, which will contribute to the modernization of infrastructure.

It should be noted that from an administrative point of view, it is much easier and more efficient when large-scale investments in the development of the territory are timed to coincide with some important event.

Conclusion

So, summing up, we would like to draw attention to the following provisions. Firstly, in world practice there are a huge number of definitions of event tourism, but the most capacious and appropriate is the definition "event tourism is understood as tourism activities associated with a variety of significant social events, as well as rare natural phenomena that attract with their uniqueness, exoticism, originality number of tourists from different countries.

Secondly, characterizing the features of event tourism, it is necessary to identify its advantages and

some disadvantages. The positive features of event tourism are: all-season, economic attractiveness, renewal of offers, multiplier effect (development of related industries) and uniqueness. Also, it should be said about the minus - the inability to predict the stability of demand for a new event.

Also, it should be said about a large number of signs, categories and classifications that complement each other, and the analysis of which allows us to identify the most effective in a particular area.

It must be said that event tourism is an important part of world progress. More and more countries are trying to get involved in the race for tourists, coming up with new events that can be either a "copy" in the tourism market or a completely new event. All this helps not only the development of the region itself, and the country as a whole, but is also a driving factor in improving the infrastructure and services.

References

1. Birzhakov M.B. Introduction to tourism. - 2014.
2. Babkin A.V. Special types of tourism: Textbook. 2008.
3. Zorin I.V., Kvartalnov V.A. Tourism as an activity: 2003.
4. Ilyina E.N. Fundamentals of tourism: 2010
5. Alekseeva O.V. Event tourism and event management 2011.
5. Zorin, I.V., Kvartalnov, V.A. Encyclopedia of tourism. 2000
6. Kvartalnov, V.A. Tourism: Theory and practice. 1998
7. Mirkin B.M. Tourism and nature conservation: a compromise is possible. 2009.